

READING SPEED AND READING COMPREHENSION OF LEARNERS IN SCIENCE -RELATED READING SELECTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15873390>

ABSTRACT

Reading is essential for understanding science concepts. Reading comprehension affects the knowledge gained from reading selections, and so does science knowledge when learners are unfamiliar with the material being read. This study investigated the reading speed and reading comprehension among Grade 8 learners using science-related reading selections. The research employed a descriptive-comparative design to analyze learners' reading performance about sex and socio-economic status. Data were gathered through a researcher-made test. Results indicated that learners exhibited average reading speeds when considered as a whole and when grouped by sex or socio-economic status. The findings of this study highlighted that learners in the same grade level have the same reading speed, and that reading speed should not be a basis for understanding the learner. The results also revealed no significant difference in reading speed across sex and socio-economic status. In terms of reading comprehension, female learners have an average level of reading comprehension. In contrast, male learners have a lower level of reading comprehension, revealing a significant difference between the sexes. On the other hand, those in poor socio-economic status have poor reading comprehension, while those in higher socio-economic statuses have average reading comprehension, revealing a significant difference across socio-economic statuses. These findings underscored the need for targeted interventions, particularly for male learners and those from lower socio-economic backgrounds. As a response, intervention program to enhance science reading comprehension is recommended. Science reading materials must also be available to learners in schools and at home to improve their reading speed and comprehension.

Keywords: *Reading Speed, Reading Comprehension, Science-related Reading Selection, Descriptive-Comparative Research Design, Central Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is fundamental in all aspects of learning, as it enables learners to gather information about what they are learning (Erya & Pustika, 2021). To make knowledge gained through reading more purposeful, one must comprehend what is being read (Caabay et al., 2024). Many can acquire new knowledge, increase creativity, and develop various skills through reading and comprehension. It is crucial to understand Science as reading skills are vital to succeeding in academics and life itself (Daguay-James & Bulusan, 2020). Reading comprehension is essential for grasping scientific concepts (Karacaoğlu & Kasap, 2023), as it enables individuals to extract meaning and insights from the complex texts that characterize scientific literature.

In the data released by the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) in 2018, the Philippines had a scientific literacy score of 357 points, lower than the average score of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), which is 489 points, putting the country second to the last of the list. According to Caraig and Quimbo (2022), several reasons exist for the country's ranking at the bottom in PISA 2018, raising questions about the ability of Filipinos, who are considered one of the best English-speaking populations. As a country that continues to fight poverty and a lack of learning resources, there is also a battle over the focus of education, particularly in reading, where most students spend more time learning vocabulary than comprehension. According to Wen et al. (2020), scientific literacy is the application of scientific knowledge to acquire, explain, and draw conclusions about phenomena and issues encountered daily. It is the ability to understand the features of Science, the awareness of how Science and technology shape the environment, and the willingness to engage in science-related issues. On the other hand, learning science is connected with math and language (Neri & Retelsdorf, 2022). Developing reading comprehension skills through language teaching seems essential for learning Science as a prerequisite (Härtig et al., 2022). In addition, according to Hackemann et al. (2022), science assessments with high linguistic demands create difficulties for students in showing their potential.

It has come to the understanding of teachers that learners who have difficulties with reading are likely to have problems with comprehension. According to Koray and Çetinkılıç (2020), reading should be integrated into science subjects as learners with low reading skills have difficulties comprehending complex ideas, especially those related to Science. In a study on the struggles of science teachers during the new normal (Geverola et al., 2022), teachers recognize that students' comprehension is challenging in their delivery. Science communicators perceive the efforts to communicate Science as poor and face challenges in communication compared to other countries (Navarro & McKinnon, 2020). The researcher observed that most learners struggling in Science also stumbled in reading comprehension and reading speed. With learners relocated from the city's slums, most do not have the necessary reading materials, let alone learning

Science. Thus, reading speed and comprehension may not be practiced at home, and science knowledge may not expand without reading materials.

According to Hendra (2021), reading speed and comprehension are crucial for reading rapidly and accurately, with proper phrasing and expression. In addition, the researcher proposed that reading faster may lead to better comprehension or vice versa. According to Windi et al. (2023), becoming familiar with words is a key component of reading speed, and proficient encoding and decoding are essential for improved comprehension. It is an understatement to say that fast readers can comprehend well while slow readers cannot. However, Busby and Dahl (2021) attributed slow readers to lower proficiency and processing. Nowadays, learners tend to answer their tests at a very fast pace. It is a wonder whether they truly understand what they are reading, given that most learners achieve lower scores in exams due to reading quickly and not fully understanding what is read. This relates to the idea that reading speed can impact reading comprehension, affecting any reading-related situation.

According to the abovementioned statements, there is an explicit assumption that reading affects science comprehension. The researcher observed that some learners who were given time to read science-related reading selections seemed to have difficulty reading, a slow reading speed, and difficulties comprehending the reading selections. Determining learners' reading speed and comprehension of what they have read is essential for selecting reading materials, especially in Science, to limit reading time, improve comprehension, and enhance understanding of science explanations, experimentation, and other classroom activities. Thus, this study focused on learners' reading speed and comprehension to create supplementary material for science-related reading.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the reading speed and comprehension of Grade 8 learners in science-related reading selection. Furthermore, the significant findings of this study will serve as the basis for developing supplementary materials to support science-related reading.

Specifically, this study sought to determine the following:

1. What is the reading speed of Grade 8 learners in science-related reading selection when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status?
2. What is the reading comprehension of Grade 8 learners in science-related reading selection when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status?
3. Is there a significant difference in the reading speed of Grade 8 learners in science-related reading selection when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status?

4. Is there a significant difference in the reading comprehension of Grade 8 learners in science-related reading selection when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status?

METHODOLOGY

Locale

The study was conducted in a public secondary school in a highly urbanized city in the central Philippines. The school has been serving the communities of relocated families with backgrounds from different parts of the city and has much to improve and make more prosperous projects. Surrounded by newly built houses and mostly starting families, the school's learners vary from those with low incomes to moderate income-generating ones. The study was conducted face-to-face, observing the health and safety protocols.

Respondents

The respondents in this study were Grade 8 learners at a large secondary school, considered a last-mile school in Negros Island, Philippines, who were officially enrolled for the academic year 2024-2025. This research employed a stratified random sampling method. Stratified random sampling is a technique for sampling in which participants are selected for a study randomly from each of the homogeneous subgroups, or strata, that comprise the population (Nguyen et al., 2019). Using Slovin's formula, one hundred forty-five (145) learners from the two hundred twenty-eight (228) Grade 8 learners participated in the study.

Instruments

The researcher conducted data-gathering procedures using a researcher-made test. The researcher-made test consists of a survey to gather demographic data, including the sex and socio-economic status of the respondents, as well as science-related reading selections and comprehension questions. To measure reading speed, respondents read two science-related selections: Reading Selection 1, "Mitosis and Meiosis" (267 words), and Reading Selection 2, "Ecosystems" (272 words), and were timed using a stopwatch. The researcher measured and recorded the reading speed of the respondents. The reading speed was characterized as slow, average, above average, and excellent (Windi et al., 2023), as seen in the table:

Table 1
Rates of Reading Speed

No	Words Per Minute	Rate of Reading
1	50 – 100	Slow
2	100 – 200	Average
3	300 – 400	Above Average
4	400	Excellent

In order to solve for the reading speed, which is the words per minute (wpm), the formula (Hendra, 2021) was used:

$$\text{Reading Speed (wpm)} = \frac{\text{Number of words}}{\text{Time (in minutes)}}$$

The second part of the data-gathering process involved answering comprehension questions with multiple-choice options from the researcher-made test to measure how much they had perceived from the reading selection about Mitosis, Meiosis, and Ecosystems. The science-related reading selection about Mitosis and Meiosis consisted of 10 questions. Similarly, the science-related reading selection about Ecosystems comprised 10 questions. The reading comprehension was then categorized as very good, good, average, bad, and very bad (Afiyah, 2022), as seen in the table:

Table 2
Reading Comprehension Score Classification

No	Comprehension Score	Classification
1	17 – 20	Very Good
2	13 – 16	Good
3	9 – 12	Average
4	5 – 8	Bad
5	1 – 4	Very Bad

The validity of an instrument refers to how well the data represents the factual findings and to the extent to which the instrument measures and assesses the relevance of an instrument (Ahmed & Ishtiaq, 2021). The researcher-made test, used to measure reading speed and comprehension in the science-related reading selection, was subjected to construct and content validity to confirm the instrument's relevance and effectiveness. Ten (10) field experts from public secondary schools were requested to validate the test in terms of its credibility and relevance as an instrument. The researcher employed the Content Validity Ratio (CVR) by Charles Lawshe and the Good and Scates Validation Tool to test for validity. The instrument was validated using the Good and Scates Validation Tool, which yielded a value of 4.8, which was interpreted as "Very Good." Meanwhile, the Content Validity Ratio (CVR) found that all items were essential.

Reliability is the degree of consistency in measurement and the extent to which it is error-free (Gidron, 2020). The researcher used Cronbach's Alpha to assess reliability. The researcher-made test was administered to respondents from the Grade 8 population for the 2024-2025 school year. The respondents who participated in the reliability test were not part of the study. The reliability of the researcher-made test is confirmed by the total value of the coefficient of correlation (r) = 0.80, which is interpreted as reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

For data collection in this study, the researcher sent a letter to the principal for permission to conduct the study. After the request was approved, the class advisers of

the respondents were informed about the test's purpose, schedule, and coverage. Before administering the test to the learners and during the Parent-Teacher Conference, parental or guardian consent was distributed, signed, and collected.

After assessing the validity and reliability of the instruments, data gathering was initiated and completed. The researcher-made test was administered to the Grade 8 learners in the classroom during the data gathering. The researcher plotted a schedule for administering the researcher-made test to the learners. The researcher administered the researcher-made test to ensure that the research objectives and the nature and privacy of the test were explained, thereby protecting the students' responses. A stopwatch was used to measure learners' reading speed, and an individual reading was conducted. The respondents were instructed to read the science reading selections, which were 267 words for Reading Selection 1, about Mitosis and Meiosis, and 272 words for Reading Selection 2, about Ecosystems. The time spent reading was recorded to interpret reading speed. The respondents were then given general instructions and an opportunity to clarify any concerns to avoid confusion before answering the researcher-made reading comprehension test.

The respondents were categorized into sex and socio-economic status. The data collected was checked, recorded, and underwent statistical treatment.

Statistical Treatment

The numerical data gathered from the instruments were subjected to specific descriptive and inferential statistical treatment.

For Problem No. 1, to determine the mean and standard deviation of the reading speed of Grade 8 learners, the respondents were timed according to words per minute. According to Hendra (2021), reading speed is calculated by dividing the number of words in a reading selection by the time it takes the reader to read it in minutes. The data were then analyzed and grouped by sex and socio-economic status.

For Problem No. 2, to determine the mean and standard deviation of the reading comprehension of Grade 8 learners, the respondents answered a researcher-made test based on science-related selection. The data were taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status.

For Problem No. 3, the t-test and One-Way ANOVA were utilized to determine the significant difference in reading speed among Grade 8 learners in science-related reading selection when taken as a whole and grouped by sex and socio-economic status, respectively.

For Problem No. 4, the Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis Test were utilized to determine the significant difference in the reading comprehension of Grade 8 learners in science-related reading selection when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status, respectively.

RESULTS

Table 3

Learners' Reading Speed in Science-Related Reading Selection when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Sex				
Male	81	129	35.55	Average
Female	64	129	37.95	Average
As a whole	145	129	36.75	Average
Socio-economic status				
Poor	80	126	35.42	Average
Low income (but not poor)	47	130	36.39	Average
Lower middle-income	13	137	47.11	Average
Middle middle class	5	151	13.62	Average
As a whole	145	129	36.75	Average

Table 4

Learners' Reading Comprehension in Science-Related Reading Selection when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status

Variables	n	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Sex				
Male	81	8.47	4.08	Bad
Female	64	10.36	3.82	Average
As a whole	145	9.41	3.95	Average
Socio-economic status				
Poor	80	8.25	3.69	Bad
Low income (but not poor)	47	10.31	3.81	Average
Lower middle-income	13	11.15	5.26	Average
Middle middle class	5	11.80	4.87	Average
As a whole	145	9.41	3.95	Average

Table 5

Significant Difference in the Reading Speed of Learners in Science-Related Reading Selection when grouped according to sex

Variable (Sex)	\bar{x}	SD	p-value	Sig at $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision
Male (n=81)	128.741	35.552	0.970	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
Female (n=64)	128.969	37.952			

* $p < 0.05$, Significant

Table 6

Significant Difference in the Reading Speed of Learners in Science-Related Reading Selection when grouped according to socio-economic status

Cases	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Sig at $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision
Socio-economic Background	4425.869	3	1475.290	1.110	0.347	Not Significant	Accept H_0
Residuals	187436.982	141	1329.340				

* $p < 0.05$, Significant

Table 7

Significant Difference in the Reading Comprehension of Learners in Science-Related Reading Selection when grouped according to sex

Variable (Sex)	\bar{x}	SD	p-value	Sig at $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision
Male (n=81)	8.469	4.084	0.002*	Significant	Reject H_0
Female (n=64)	10.359	3.815			

* $p < 0.05$, Significant

Table 8

Significant Difference in the Reading Comprehension of Learners in Science-related Reading Selection when grouped according to socio-economic status

Factor	Statistic	df	p-value	Sig at $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision
Socio-economic Background	12.642	3	0.005*	Significant	Reject H_0

* $p < 0.05$, Significant

DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the reading speed of Grade 8 learners in science-related reading selection when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status?

Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviation of reading speed and the number of study participants grouped by sex. The mean reading speed of both male and female learners was 129, attaining an Average reading speed with a standard deviation of 35.55 and 37.95, respectively. When taken as a whole, the mean reading speed was 129, with a standard deviation of 36.75, indicating an average reading speed.

Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviation of reading speed and the number of learners when considered collectively and grouped by socio-economic status. Learners obtained an interpretation of Average reading speed: Poor socio-economic status (M=125; SD=35.42), Low income (but not poor) (M=130; SD=36.39), Lower middle-income learners (M=137; SD=47.11), and Middle middle-class learners (M=151; SD=13.62).

Learners in different grade levels may have similar reading speeds, with minimal differences between those fluent in reading and those competent in Science. There are cases in which learners read out loud at a similar pace, with few students reading at their own pace. This is often encountered when the teacher asks students to read what is written on the board or displayed on a classroom television or projector screen. However, when learners read individually, they follow their own pace. Additionally, as learners acquire more words and become more familiar with the topic, they tend to read faster. Reading speed may also vary depending on how familiar learners are with the words and as they progress to higher grade levels. Reading speed may vary by grade level, as most promoted learners acquire more vocabulary.

Learners with lower family incomes tend to read more slowly compared to those with higher family incomes, which means that learners from underprivileged families may have factors that hinder their opportunity to enhance their reading skills, such as reading speed. Some common factors that could lead to a learner becoming a slow reader would be the unavailability of reading materials to practice at home. Even at home, learners should be able to practice reading so that by the time they have school, they can apply what they have learned. However, schools and libraries provide reading materials for learners during their free time. Most learners nowadays would rather spend their time on leisure than take a book and read. Additionally, not all reading materials from school can be taken home.

According to Støle et al. (2020), some individuals read thoughtfully to understand better, which may reduce their reading speed. This means that learners who read more slowly than others are trying to know what they are reading, while those who read quickly may not be able to comprehend it well due to their reading speed. However, as Windi et al. (2023) mentioned, a fast reader is not always an efficient reader, nor is a slow reader an inefficient reader. Learners may read at a faster or slower speed. Still, their understanding of the reading material depends on how they digest the words and sentences and make connections. There is a view that learners should be aware of the words they read and connect them to grasp the idea of the reading material, as reading speed is influenced by an individual's awareness of their reading process (Klimovich et al., 2023).

In addition, learners from disadvantaged families are less likely to develop fundamental skills such as reading (Buckingham et al., 2023). Those learners from underprivileged families would not have the appropriate reading materials to improve their reading speed at home. However, according to Ukpebor (2020), learners have a poor reading culture, irrespective of the availability of reading materials. Though it was

mentioned by Romeo et al. (2022) that due to poor socio-economic status, learners may not have access to resources, experiences, and exposure to improve their reading skills, such as reading speed, the unavailability of materials becomes a significant factor that learners in poor socio-economic status may not have the capacity to expand their knowledge in Science and reading.

Research Question 2. What is the reading comprehension of Grade 8 learners in science-related reading selection when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status?

Table 4 presents the mean and standard deviation of reading comprehension and the number of study participants grouped by sex. As a whole, the mean reading comprehension score was 9.41, which had an Average interpretation. When grouped according to sex, the reading comprehension of the male learners was 8.47 (SD=4.08), obtaining a Bad comprehension score, while the reading comprehension of the female learners was 10.36 (SD=3.82), interpreted as Average.

It also presents the mean and standard deviation of reading comprehension and the number of learners grouped by socio-economic status. As a whole, the mean reading comprehension score was 9.41, which had an Average interpretation, and, when grouped according to socio-economic status, the learners with Poor socio-economic status had an interpretation of Bad comprehension (M=8.25; SD=3.69), the learners with Low income (but not poor) was Average (M=10.32; SD=3.81), the Lower middle-income learners was Average (M=11.15; SD=5.26), and the Middle middle-class learners was Average (M=11.80; SD=4.87).

According to the results, male learners scored lower on the reading comprehension test than female learners. The results implied that female learners understand what is being read better than male learners. It has often been observed that female learners tend to read more accurately compared to male learners. There are cases in which male learners read shyly in the classroom when they are chosen to read a specific text. In Science, learners' improved reading comprehension is attributed to their interest and motivation. It implies that female learners have a greater interest in reading science-related selections and are more motivated to learn than male learners.

On the other hand, according to the reading comprehension results, when grouped by socio-economic status, the lower the socio-economic status, the lower the mean reading comprehension score. This implies that learners from the poor socio-economic class have lower comprehension of science and reading than those from higher socio-economic classes. One observable factor of poor comprehension is the unavailability of materials and the inability to practice at home. Learners from poor socio-economic backgrounds may not have access to science reading materials at home, hindering their ability to expand their knowledge and develop an interest in Science. Learners may be unable to practice at home due to insufficient materials. However, the lack of guidance from family members may also contribute to poor comprehension. Not all family members are skilled in reading, and not all parents are at home to guide their learners in practice.

The mean score for reading comprehension among female learners in the study was higher than that of the male learners, a finding similar to Soysal (2022). According to Putri and Melani (2022), females tend to have better reading comprehension than males due to several factors, including background knowledge, attitude, and motivation. Girls generally enjoyed the social aspects of reading more than boys. It is the attitude of the learners that becomes a factor in their reading comprehension. Female and male learners have different motivations and attitudes toward activities at home or in an institution. However, according to Muntoni et al. (2020), noting that female learners are better at reading comprehension than male learners may affect the bearing of learners' motivation and achievement as individuals and their performance in the classroom. In this study, female learners appear more motivated to engage in science and reading than male learners. However, given the awareness of low reading comprehension, male learners should receive an intervention or motivation to improve their reading skills, especially when dealing with science content.

According to Koyuncu and Firat (2020), the index of economic, social, and cultural status is a significant factor affecting reading literacy, including learners' reading comprehension. Families with low incomes may struggle to provide the necessary educational supplements for their children, such as books for reading, to enhance their reading comprehension and reading ability. More than half of the learners with a family income of less than Php 12,030 per month had a Bad comprehension score, indicating that among the most disadvantaged children, family income is strongly related to the structure of a child's brain and reading ability. This would also mean that the families could not provide materials for learners to read about Science or other subjects due to low income. However, Cooper & Stewart (2020) noted that household income significantly influences learners' achievement, suggesting that other factors may also impact learners' reading comprehension in the scientific area. Low motivation and low self-efficacy in science comprehension may also be influenced by less parental involvement or uninvolved parenting rather than just family income. Low-income parents often face time and energy constraints related to work, which results in less engagement with their learners (Sengonul, 2022).

Research Question 3. Is there a significant difference in the reading speed of Grade 8 learners in science-related reading selection when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status?

Table 5 shows a significant difference in the reading speed of learners in science-related reading selections when grouped by sex, resulting in no significant difference in reading speed between male and female Grade 8 learners ($p = 0.970 > \alpha = 0.05$), therefore accepting the null hypothesis.

The results suggested that reading speed may not affect the understanding of science-related reading selections or the increase in learners' motivation toward Science. The data indicated that science-related selections have equal levels of engagement among learners. Science content can capture the interest of male and female learners when presented in an accessible and appropriate manner. However, attitudes toward

Science may vary between male and female learners. Reading comprehension programs should integrate text-to-text resources demonstrating the importance of reading in Science, with examples for both forces. The matter of motivation and increasing interest in both reading and Science must be addressed.

According to Álvarez-Cañizo et al. (2020), individuals should train their skills to increase their reading speed and gather important information from all types of texts. In contrast, Memisevic et al. (2020) investigated how learners remove a sound from a word or a phoneme, thereby creating a new word, which affects an individual's reading speed and comprehension. These contrasting perspectives highlight that while promoting reading speed has advantages for academic efficiency, it must not negatively affect the accuracy and understanding of what is being read. Learners must be trained not only to read faster but also to maintain efficient comprehension. Reading interventions in science should focus on understanding while ensuring students do not rush through the ideas. Reading complex texts in science subjects is crucial, as missing a single term or concept can significantly alter comprehension. According to Wahyuni et al. (2020), reading interests and learning motivation should be instilled in the learning process to maintain and improve student learning outcomes.

Table 6 shows that there is no significant difference in the reading speed of learners in science-related reading selections when grouped by socio-economic status ($p = 0.347 > \alpha = 0.05$); therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Learners from different socio-economic backgrounds have varying reading speeds in reading science-related selections. The results suggested that, at least in terms of reading speed, factors other than the lack of access to reading materials and the absence of background support also influence reading speed. Other factors affecting reading speed in science-related selections include reading strategies, science motivations, and prior knowledge of Science. Science reading interventions are necessary to enhance reading speed, targeting not only socio-economic status but also individual performance or the specific needs of each learner.

Learners with lower family incomes tend to read more slowly due to factors such as a low-quality early literacy environment in their homes, which increases the risk of a child struggling with reading (Buckingham et al., 2023). The lack of a reading foundation hinders the development of a learner's comprehension and fluency. Consequently, learners from lower-income families are disadvantaged at school (Lindner, 2022). As it is difficult to acquire resources, academic content becomes more complex, particularly in subjects like Science, creating a wider gap in reading ability. Schools need to compensate for some learners' literacy gaps, given that most children come from poor socio-economic backgrounds. While the overall reading speed appears average across socio-economic status groups, learners from low-income households must have programs that can motivate and spark their interest in science reading. Through supplemental reading materials, according to Chen et al. (2022), learners achieved significant improvements in their interests in Science and reading. Free take-home science reading materials would

spark individual beliefs and attitudes about knowledge and knowing about the evolving nature and methods of Science.

Research Question 4. Is there a significant difference in the reading comprehension of Grade 8 learners in science-related reading selection when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex and socio-economic status?

Table 7 shows that there is a significant difference in the reading comprehension of learners in science-related reading selections when grouped by sex ($p = 0.002 < \alpha = 0.05$), and therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The reading speed is incomparable to reading comprehension. Both sexes may exhibit similarities in their reading speed; however, in terms of reading comprehension, female learners tend to comprehend better than their male counterparts. The results revealed that female learners performed significantly better in reading comprehension. This suggests that reading speed does not guarantee understanding and that male-female differences in processing and engaging with reading science-related selection may exist. This features a gap that differences may influence interest, strategies, or motivation. Besides the result that females have better comprehension, there is an urgency to recognize the need to benefit male learners through comprehension interventions, which may include scaffolding, boosting motivation, and driving interest in Science and reading.

Reading science-related selection needs a greater effort and a process of understanding. According to Koray and Çetinkılıç (2020), the habit of reading should be instilled in all countries to develop critical thinking skills for analysis, synthesis, and evaluation, which are incorporated in Science and other courses. There is a demand for understanding science texts, particularly among learners with weaker inferential or integrative skills. Educators must go beyond instruction and emphasize teaching comprehension strategies, particularly to learners who need scaffolding in beginner ideas of Science and reading. Science teachers should make topics relevant by implementing project-based learning, connecting science reading selections to real-life experiences, utilizing diverse media in teaching, and fostering an encouraging classroom environment (Markula & Aksela, 2022). Instructional materials should support active engagement to encourage learners to process ideas deeply (Campbell & Lee, 2021) rather than focusing solely on speed and efficiency. All learners, regardless of sex, should develop the skills to comprehend complex scientific concepts effectively.

Table 8 shows a significant difference in learners' reading comprehension in science-related reading selection when grouped according to socio-economic status ($p = 0.005 > \alpha = 0.05$), and therefore the null hypothesis was rejected.

Schools, or even the entire education sector, should implement reading interventions and provide additional support to learners from low-income or poor socio-economic backgrounds. Learners can also easily access free science reading materials, which allow them to read and develop an interest in science at home. As part of an

institution, non-science and language teachers should also lend a hand in learners' reading sessions on topics in Science and other areas. Science teachers should also incorporate scaffolding into their discussions of science-related reading selections, especially for learners who are underprivileged in education, to make the content more comprehensible for all learners. The results of this study should prioritize support for disadvantaged learners to bridge the comprehension and educational gap.

According to a study by Wawire et al. (2024), socio-economic status and access to resources significantly impact learners' reading fluency and comprehension. According to Kilag et al. (2023), an effective reading program and providing reading materials can help promote frequent reading habits and overcome reading challenges. However, learners of higher socio-economic status could afford reading materials (Sultan et al., 2020) such as science books, almanacs, encyclopedias, and dictionaries. They could hire tutors for more advanced study while staying in a conducive learning room. Therefore, learners from lower socio-economic statuses should be prioritized in implementation programs, as the lack of appropriate reading materials, living in spaces that are disadvantageous for studying and having fewer opportunities to advance are most common among these learners.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions:

Reading speed is similar to that of learners at the same grade level. Although the males have a slightly lower mean than females, both reading speeds are Average. Suppose there is no guarantee that a fast reader is an efficient reader, a slow reader, or an inefficient reader. In that case, there is also no guarantee that a female learner could read faster than a male learner or that a male learner could read faster than a female learner. The data indicate that reading speed in science-related selections has equal levels of engagement for learners. Thus, without sacrificing reading comprehension for speed, slow readers in the classroom must be addressed and given guided practice to catch up with their peers.

In another concept, the reading speeds of learners classified under different socio-economic statuses are similar. While the reading speeds of learners classified under different socio-economic statuses have minimal differences, the learners read at an Average speed. However, learners from lower-income families tend to read slower than those from higher-income families. This means that learners from underprivileged families face factors such as the unavailability of reading materials to practice at home, which can deteriorate their reading skills, including reading speed.

Additionally, there was no significant difference in the reading speed between male and female learners. Promoting reading speed has advantages but should not adversely affect understanding Science in science-related selections. Learners must be trained not only to read faster but also to maintain efficient and better comprehension. Reading

interventions in the science area should target understanding and must capture the interest of male and female learners.

Furthermore, there was no significant difference in reading speed among learners from different socio-economic statuses. Some learners read faster or slower than others. Still, when considered as a whole or by sex or socio-economic status, the reading speed of learners is Average. It may vary slightly depending on their reading and science skills. Learners from low socio-economic backgrounds often lack access to essential materials and learning opportunities. The lack of a reading foundation will also affect the understanding of science concepts and put learners at a disadvantage. Schools need to compensate for the educational gaps that some learners have. There should be programs that can motivate and interest learners in science reading. Science reading materials can spark learners' interests and encourage them to achieve improvements in both Science and reading.

Based on the Reading Comprehension Score Classification table, female learners have an Average comprehension score. In contrast, male learners have a Bad comprehension score in the science-related reading selection. Therefore, female learners read and understand better than their male counterparts. Science content should capture the interest of male and female learners. Reading comprehension programs should integrate science texts that relate to real-life applications to reinforce interest, especially for male learners. Male learners should be recognized in comprehension interventions, which may include scaffolding, boosting motivation, and driving interest in Science and reading. Strategies to enhance reading interests in Science should be infused, together with learning motivation, in reading selections to improve student learning outcomes.

On the other hand, when grouped according to socio-economic status, learners from the lowest income group were classified as having a Bad comprehension score. In contrast, the rest of the learners had an average comprehension score. Some learners can afford reading materials at home, hire tutors for more advanced study, and have a conducive room for learning. However, the data showed that many learners from lower socio-economic backgrounds, especially in public schools, likely lack access to appropriate reading materials, have fewer opportunities to advance in programs, and live in disadvantaged studying spaces. Implementing science reading interventions and providing additional support to learners from low-income backgrounds or those with poor socio-economic backgrounds should be accomplished. Science reading materials should be free and easily accessible to learners for reading and fostering a greater interest in Science. Scaffolding should be included in science-related reading selection discussions, especially for learners who are underprivileged in education, to help them strengthen their science concepts. The results of this study should prioritize support for disadvantaged learners, such as male learners and those from low socio-economic backgrounds, to bridge the gap in science literacy and comprehension.

Recommendations

This study determined learners' reading speed and comprehension of science-related reading selections. The results of this study may provide valuable information to enhance literacy skills in Science and improve strategies for bridging the gap between reading and science comprehension. Science reading materials can be utilized in programs such as Catch-up Fridays or other reading initiatives to engage learners and foster a deeper understanding of the material being read.

This study identified materials that could benefit learners, particularly male learners and those with low socio-economic status, who often struggle with poor reading comprehension. Providing free access to reading materials and science-related reading selections may also enhance learners' reading abilities.

Through the data from this research, Science teachers may gain insights into how reading speed and reading comprehension affect learner performance in the classroom and identify strategies to improve understanding of Science. This research may also benefit non-science teachers, especially language teachers, as reading speed and comprehension also impact learning in various school subjects.

This study may also help learners recognize the importance of reading, not just in language studies but also in Science. This study may serve as a basis for future research on reading speed, reading comprehension, science-related reading selection, and other related application areas.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study subscribed to the principles of voluntary participation in research, implying that the respondents might withdraw from this research at any time. Informed consent, which means that the respondents must at all times, be well informed about the research process and purposes and should give consent to his/her participation in this research.

Safety, involvement put differently, that the researcher makes sure that respondents should not be placed at risk or harm of any kind. Privacy means that the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents should be protected at all times. Moreover, trust, which implies that the respondents will not be subjected to any acts of deception or betrayal in this research process or its published outcomes and has the right to know the conclusion of this study.

Likewise, the researchers understand what plagiarism entails and are aware of the school's policy in this regard. The researcher undertakes not to make use of another person's previous work without recognition or to submit it as our own. The researcher also manages not to allow anyone to copy our output to use it as their work.

Acknowledgments

The researcher wants to convey her immeasurable appreciation and deepest gratitude for the help and support of the administrators of the school to where she graduated, her research adviser, the Dean of Graduate School, the members of the pre-oral and final defense panel, the school head, the co-teachers, the validators, the respondents, and above all to the Almighty God whose faith and contribution made this academic endeavor a success.

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